

Supplemental Material

Can green hydrogen support fossil fuel workers? Examining workforce transition pathways in oil and gas communities

Table S1: Custom NAICS industry aggregation for use in modeling electrolyzer workforce development impacts

AGGREGATED INDUSTRY NAME	NAICS 528 INDUSTRY CODE	DESCRIPTION
AGRICULTURE	1	Oilseed farming
	2	Grain farming
	3	Vegetable and melon farming
	4	Fruit farming
	5	Tree nut farming
	6	Greenhouse, nursery, and floriculture production
	7	Tobacco farming
	8	Cotton farming
	9	Sugarcane and sugar beet farming
	10	All other crop farming
	11	Beef cattle ranching and farming, including feedlots and dual-purpose ranching and farming
	12	Dairy cattle and milk production
	13	Poultry and egg production
	14	Animal production, except cattle and poultry and eggs
	15	Forestry, forest products, and timber tract production
	16	Commercial logging
	17	Commercial fishing
	18	Commercial hunting and trapping
	19	Support activities for agriculture and forestry
OIL AND GAS EXTRACTION	20	Oil and gas extraction
	30	Drilling oil and gas wells
	31	Support activities for oil and gas operations
COAL MINING	21	Coal mining
NON-FUEL MINING	22	Copper, nickel, lead, and zinc mining
	23	Iron ore mining
	24	Gold ore and silver ore mining
	25	Other metal ore mining

	26	Stone mining and quarrying
	27	Sand and gravel mining
	28	Other clay, ceramic, refractory minerals mining
	29	Other nonmetallic mineral mining and quarrying
	32	Metal mining services
	33	Other nonmetallic minerals services
MANUFACTURING CONSTRUCTION	46	Construction of new manufacturing structures
	45	Construction of new health care structures
	47	Construction of new power and communication structures
	48	Construction of new educational and vocational structures
	49	Construction of new highways and streets
GENERAL CONSTRUCTION	50	Construction of new commercial structures, including farm structures
	51	Construction of other new nonresidential structures
	55	Maintenance and repair construction of nonresidential structures
	56	Maintenance and repair construction of residential structures
	57	Maintenance and repair construction of highways, streets, bridges, and tunnels
	34	Electric power generation - Hydroelectric
	35	Electric power generation - Fossil fuel
	36	Electric power generation - Nuclear
	37	Electric power generation - Solar
ELECTRIC POWER GENERATION	38	Electric power generation - Wind
	39	Electric power generation - Geothermal
	40	Electric power generation - Biomass
	41	Electric power generation - All other
	42	Electric power transmission and distribution
WATER UTILITIES	44	Water, sewage and other systems
OTHER UTILITIES	43	Natural gas distribution
	401	Pipeline transportation

GAS AND CHEMICAL MANUFACTURING	152	Industrial gas manufacturing
	154	Other basic inorganic chemical manufacturing
	155	Other basic organic chemical manufacturing
METAL PROCESSING	241	Metal heat treating
	242	Metal coating and nonprecious engraving
	243	Electroplating, anodizing, and coloring metal
ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT	296	Semiconductor and related device manufacturing
	297	Capacitor, resistor, coil, transformer, and other inductor manufacturing
	298	Electronic connector manufacturing
	303	Industrial process variable instruments manufacturing
	314	Power, distribution, and specialty transformer manufacturing
	315	Motor and generator manufacturing
	316	Switchgear and switchboard apparatus manufacturing
	317	Relay and industrial control manufacturing
	318	Battery manufacturing
	319	Fiber optic cable manufacturing
	320	Other communication and energy wire manufacturing
	321	Wiring device manufacturing
	229	Plate work manufacturing
	230	Metal window and door manufacturing
	FABRICATED METALS	231
232		Ornamental and architectural metal work manufacturing
233		Power boiler and heat exchanger manufacturing
234		Metal tank (heavy gauge) manufacturing
260		All other industrial machinery manufacturing
MACHINERY	270	Turbine and turbine generator set units manufacturing
	271	Speed changer, industrial high-speed drive, and gear manufacturing
	272	Mechanical power transmission equipment manufacturing
	283	Industrial process furnace and oven manufacturing

	284	Fluid power cylinder and actuator manufacturing	
	285	Fluid power pump and motor manufacturing	
PROFESSIONAL SERVICES	437	Legal services	
	438	Accounting, tax preparation, bookkeeping, and payroll services	
	439	Architectural, engineering, and related services	
	440	Specialized design services	
	442	Computer systems design services	
	443	Other computer related services, including facilities management	
	444	Management consulting services	
	445	Environmental and other technical consulting services	
	446	Scientific research and development services	
	447	Advertising, public relations, and related services	
	450	All other miscellaneous professional, scientific, and technical services	
	WHOLESALE TRADE	375	Wholesale - Motor vehicle and motor vehicle parts and supplies
		376	Wholesale - Professional and commercial equipment and supplies
377		Wholesale - Household appliances and electrical and electronic goods	
378		Wholesale - Machinery, equipment, and supplies	
379		Wholesale - Other durable goods merchant wholesalers	
380		Wholesale - Drugs and druggists' sundries	
381		Wholesale - Grocery and related product wholesalers	
382		Wholesale - Petroleum and petroleum products	
383		Wholesale - Other nondurable goods merchant wholesalers	
384		Wholesale - Wholesale electronic markets and agents and brokers	
RETAIL TRADE	385	Retail - Motor vehicle and parts dealers	
	386	Retail - Furniture and home furnishings stores	
	387	Retail - Electronics and appliance stores	

	388	Retail - Building material and garden equipment and supplies stores
	389	Retail - Food and beverage stores
	390	Retail - Health and personal care stores
	391	Retail - Gasoline stores
	392	Retail - Clothing and clothing accessories stores
	393	Retail - Sporting goods, hobby, musical instrument and book stores
	394	Retail - General merchandise stores
	395	Retail - Miscellaneous store retailers
FINANCE, INSURANCE, AND REAL ESTATE	421	Nondepository credit intermediation and related activities
	422	Securities and commodity contracts intermediation and brokerage
	423	Monetary authorities and depository credit intermediation
	424	Other financial investment activities
	425	Direct life insurance carriers
	426	Insurance carriers, except direct life
	427	Insurance agencies, brokerages, and related activities
	428	Funds, trusts, and other financial vehicles
	429	Other real estate
	430	Tenant-occupied housing
	431	Owner-occupied housing
OTHER MANUFACTURING	58	Dog and cat food manufacturing
	59	Other animal food manufacturing
	60	Flour milling
	61	Rice milling
	62	Malt manufacturing
	63	Wet corn milling
	64	Soybean and other oilseed processing
	65	Fats and oils refining and blending
	66	Breakfast cereal manufacturing
67	Beet sugar manufacturing	

68	Sugar cane mills and refining
69	Nonchocolate confectionery manufacturing
70	Chocolate and confectionery manufacturing from cacao beans
71	Confectionery manufacturing from purchased chocolate
72	Frozen fruits, juices and vegetables manufacturing
73	Frozen specialties manufacturing
74	Canned fruits and vegetables manufacturing
75	Canned specialties
76	Dehydrated food products manufacturing
77	Cheese manufacturing
78	Dry, condensed, and evaporated dairy product manufacturing
79	Fluid milk manufacturing
80	Creamery butter manufacturing
81	Ice cream and frozen dessert manufacturing
82	Frozen cakes and other pastries manufacturing
83	Poultry processing
84	Animal, except poultry, slaughtering
85	Meat processed from carcasses
86	Rendering and meat byproduct processing
87	Seafood product preparation and packaging
88	Bread and bakery product, except frozen, manufacturing
89	Cookie and cracker manufacturing
90	Dry pasta, mixes, and dough manufacturing
91	Tortilla manufacturing
92	Roasted nuts and peanut butter manufacturing
93	Other snack food manufacturing
94	Coffee and tea manufacturing
95	Flavoring syrup and concentrate manufacturing
96	Mayonnaise, dressing, and sauce manufacturing
97	Spice and extract manufacturing

98	All other food manufacturing
99	Bottled and canned soft drinks & water
100	Manufactured ice
101	Breweries
102	Wineries
103	Distilleries
104	Tobacco manufacturing
105	Fiber, yarn, and thread mills
106	Broadwoven fabric mills
107	Narrow fabric mills and schiffli machine embroidery
108	Nonwoven fabric mills
109	Knit fabric mills
110	Textile and fabric finishing mills
111	Fabric coating mills
112	Carpet and rug mills
113	Curtain and linen mills
114	Textile bag and canvas mills
115	Rope, cordage, twine, tire cord and tire fabric mills
116	Other textile product mills
117	Apparel knitting mills
118	Cut and sew apparel contractors
119	Cut and sew apparel manufacturing (except contractors)
120	Apparel accessories and other apparel manufacturing
121	Leather and hide tanning and finishing
122	Footwear manufacturing
123	Other leather and allied product manufacturing
124	Sawmills
125	Wood preservation
126	Veneer and plywood manufacturing
127	Engineered wood member and truss manufacturing
128	Reconstituted wood product manufacturing

129	Wood windows and door manufacturing
130	Cut stock, resawing lumber, and planing
131	Other millwork, including flooring
132	Wood container and pallet manufacturing
133	Manufactured home (mobile home) manufacturing
134	Prefabricated wood building manufacturing
135	All other miscellaneous wood product manufacturing
136	Pulp mills
137	Paper mills
138	Paperboard mills
139	Paperboard container manufacturing
140	Paper bag and coated and treated paper manufacturing
141	Stationery product manufacturing
142	Sanitary paper product manufacturing
143	All other converted paper product manufacturing
144	Printing
145	Support activities for printing
146	Petroleum refineries
147	Asphalt paving mixture and block manufacturing
148	Asphalt shingle and coating materials manufacturing
149	Petroleum lubricating oil and grease manufacturing
150	All other petroleum and coal products manufacturing
151	Petrochemical manufacturing
153	Synthetic dye and pigment manufacturing
156	Plastics material and resin manufacturing
157	Synthetic rubber manufacturing
158	Artificial and synthetic fibers and filaments manufacturing
159	Nitrogenous fertilizer manufacturing
160	Phosphatic fertilizer manufacturing
161	Fertilizer mixing
162	Pesticide and other agricultural chemical manufacturing

163	Medicinal and botanical manufacturing
164	Pharmaceutical preparation manufacturing
165	In-vitro diagnostic substance manufacturing
166	Biological product (except diagnostic) manufacturing
167	Paint and coating manufacturing
168	Adhesive manufacturing
169	Soap and other detergent manufacturing
170	Polish and other sanitation good manufacturing
171	Surface active agent manufacturing
172	Toilet preparation manufacturing
173	Printing ink manufacturing
174	Explosives manufacturing
175	Custom compounding of purchased resins
176	Photographic film and chemical manufacturing
177	Other miscellaneous chemical product manufacturing
178	Plastics packaging materials and unlaminated film and sheet manufacturing
179	Unlaminated plastics profile shape manufacturing
180	Plastics pipe and pipe fitting manufacturing
181	Laminated plastics plate, sheet (except packaging), and shape manufacturing
182	Polystyrene foam product manufacturing
183	Urethane and other foam product (except polystyrene) manufacturing
184	Plastics bottle manufacturing
185	Other plastics product manufacturing
186	Tire manufacturing
187	Rubber and plastics hoses and belting manufacturing
188	Other rubber product manufacturing
189	Pottery, ceramics, and plumbing fixture manufacturing
190	Brick, tile, and other structural clay product manufacturing
191	Flat glass manufacturing

192	Other pressed and blown glass and glassware manufacturing
193	Glass container manufacturing
194	Glass product manufacturing made of purchased glass
195	Cement manufacturing
196	Ready-mix concrete manufacturing
197	Concrete block and brick manufacturing
198	Concrete pipe manufacturing
199	Other concrete product manufacturing
200	Lime manufacturing
201	Gypsum product manufacturing
202	Abrasive product manufacturing
203	Cut stone and stone product manufacturing
204	Ground or treated mineral and earth manufacturing
205	Mineral wool manufacturing
206	Miscellaneous nonmetallic mineral products manufacturing
207	Iron and steel mills and ferroalloy manufacturing
208	Iron, steel pipe and tube manufacturing from purchased steel
209	Rolled steel shape manufacturing
210	Steel wire drawing
211	Alumina refining and primary aluminum production
212	Secondary smelting and alloying of aluminum
213	Aluminum sheet, plate, and foil manufacturing
214	Other aluminum rolling, drawing and extruding
215	Nonferrous metal (exc aluminum) smelting and refining
216	Copper rolling, drawing, extruding and alloying
217	Nonferrous metal, except copper and aluminum, shaping
218	Secondary processing of other nonferrous metals
219	Ferrous metal foundries
220	Nonferrous metal foundries
221	Custom roll forming

222	Metal crown, closure, and other metal stamping (except automotive)
223	Iron and steel forging
224	Nonferrous forging
225	Cutlery, utensil, pot, and pan manufacturing
226	Handtool manufacturing
227	Prefabricated metal buildings and components manufacturing
228	Fabricated structural metal manufacturing
235	Metal cans manufacturing
236	Metal barrels, drums and pails manufacturing
237	Hardware manufacturing
238	Spring and wire product manufacturing
239	Machine shops
240	Turned product and screw, nut, and bolt manufacturing
244	Valve and fittings, other than plumbing, manufacturing
245	Plumbing fixture fitting and trim manufacturing
246	Ball and roller bearing manufacturing
247	Small arms ammunition manufacturing
248	Ammunition, except for small arms, manufacturing
249	Small arms, ordnance, and accessories manufacturing
250	Fabricated pipe and pipe fitting manufacturing
251	Other fabricated metal manufacturing
252	Farm machinery and equipment manufacturing
253	Lawn and garden equipment manufacturing
254	Construction machinery manufacturing
255	Mining machinery and equipment manufacturing
256	Oil and gas field machinery and equipment manufacturing
257	Semiconductor machinery manufacturing
258	Food product machinery manufacturing
259	Sawmill, woodworking, and paper machinery
261	Commercial and service industry machinery manufacturing

262	Industrial and commercial fan and blower and air purification equipment manufacturing
263	Heating equipment (except warm air furnaces) manufacturing
264	Air conditioning, refrigeration, and warm air heating equipment manufacturing
265	Industrial mold manufacturing
266	Special tool, die, jig, and fixture manufacturing
267	Cutting tool and machine tool accessory manufacturing
268	Machine tool manufacturing
269	Rolling mill and other metalworking machinery manufacturing
273	Other engine equipment manufacturing
274	Measuring, dispensing, and other pumping equipment manufacturing
275	Air and gas compressor manufacturing
276	Elevator and moving stairway manufacturing
277	Conveyor and conveying equipment manufacturing
278	Overhead cranes, hoists, and monorail systems manufacturing
279	Industrial truck, trailer, and stacker manufacturing
280	Power-driven handtool manufacturing
281	Welding and soldering equipment manufacturing
282	Packaging machinery manufacturing
286	Scales, balances, and miscellaneous general purpose machinery manufacturing
287	Electronic computer manufacturing
288	Computer storage device manufacturing
289	Computer terminals and other computer peripheral equipment manufacturing
290	Telephone apparatus manufacturing
291	Broadcast and wireless communications equipment manufacturing
292	Other communications equipment manufacturing
293	Audio and video equipment manufacturing

294	Printed circuit assembly (electronic assembly) manufacturing
295	Bare printed circuit board manufacturing
299	Other electronic component manufacturing
300	Electromedical and electrotherapeutic apparatus manufacturing
301	Search, detection, and navigation instruments manufacturing
302	Automatic environmental control manufacturing
304	Totalizing fluid meter and counting device manufacturing
305	Electricity and signal testing instruments manufacturing
306	Analytical laboratory instrument manufacturing
307	Irradiation apparatus manufacturing
308	Watch, clock, and other measuring and controlling device manufacturing
309	Manufacturing and reproducing magnetic and optical media
310	Electric lamp bulb and part manufacturing
311	Lighting fixture manufacturing
312	Small electrical appliance manufacturing
313	Major household appliance manufacturing
322	Carbon and graphite product manufacturing
323	All other miscellaneous electrical equipment and component manufacturing
324	Automobile and light duty motor vehicle manufacturing
325	Heavy duty truck manufacturing
326	Motor vehicle body manufacturing
327	Truck trailer manufacturing
328	Motor home manufacturing
329	Travel trailer and camper manufacturing
330	Motor vehicle gasoline engine and engine parts manufacturing
331	Motor vehicle electrical and electronic equipment manufacturing

332	Motor vehicle transmission and power train parts manufacturing
333	Motor vehicle seating and interior trim manufacturing
334	Motor vehicle metal stamping
335	Other motor vehicle parts manufacturing
336	Motor vehicle steering, suspension component (except spring), and brake systems manufacturing
337	Aircraft manufacturing
338	Aircraft engine and engine parts manufacturing
339	Other aircraft parts and auxiliary equipment manufacturing
340	Guided missile and space vehicle manufacturing
341	Propulsion units and parts for space vehicles and guided missiles manufacturing
342	Railroad rolling stock manufacturing
343	Ship building and repairing
344	Boat building
345	Motorcycle, bicycle, and parts manufacturing
346	Military armored vehicle, tank, and tank component manufacturing
347	All other transportation equipment manufacturing
348	Wood kitchen cabinet and countertop manufacturing
349	Upholstered household furniture manufacturing
350	Nonupholstered wood household furniture manufacturing
351	Other household nonupholstered furniture manufacturing
352	Institutional furniture manufacturing
353	Wood office furniture manufacturing
354	Custom architectural woodwork and millwork
355	Office furniture, except wood, manufacturing
356	Showcase, partition, shelving, and locker manufacturing
357	Mattress manufacturing
358	Blind and shade manufacturing
359	Surgical and medical instrument manufacturing
360	Surgical appliance and supplies manufacturing

**OTHER
TRANSPORTATION**

361	Dental equipment and supplies manufacturing
362	Ophthalmic goods manufacturing
363	Dental laboratories
364	Jewelry and silverware manufacturing
365	Sporting and athletic goods manufacturing
366	Doll, toy, and game manufacturing
367	Office supplies (except paper) manufacturing
368	Sign manufacturing
369	Gasket, packing, and sealing device manufacturing
370	Musical instrument manufacturing
371	Fasteners, buttons, needles, and pins manufacturing
372	Broom, brush, and mop manufacturing
373	Burial casket manufacturing
374	All other miscellaneous manufacturing
396	Air transportation
397	Rail transportation
398	Water transportation
399	Truck transportation
511	State government passenger transit
514	Local government passenger transit
515	Local government electric utilities

**MISCELLANEOUS
SERVICES**

52	Construction of new single-family residential structures
53	Construction of new multifamily residential structures
54	Construction of other new residential structures
400	Transit and ground passenger transportation
402	Scenic and sightseeing transportation and support activities for transportation
403	Couriers and messengers
404	Warehousing and storage
405	Newspaper publishers
406	Periodical publishers
407	Book publishers

408	Directory, mailing list, and other publishers
409	Greeting card publishing
410	Software publishers
411	Motion picture and video industries
412	Sound recording industries
413	Radio and television broadcasting
414	Cable and other subscription programming
415	Wired telecommunications carriers
416	Wireless telecommunications carriers (except satellite)
417	Satellite, telecommunications resellers, and all other telecommunications
418	Data processing, hosting, and related services
419	News syndicates, libraries, archives and all other information services
420	Internet publishing and broadcasting and web search portals
449	Veterinary services
432	Automotive equipment rental and leasing
433	General and consumer goods rental except video tapes and discs
434	Video tape and disc rental
435	Commercial and industrial machinery and equipment rental and leasing
448	Photographic services
436	Lessors of nonfinancial intangible assets
441	Custom computer programming services
451	Management of companies and enterprises
452	Office administrative services
453	Facilities support services
454	Employment services
455	Business support services
456	Travel arrangement and reservation services
457	Investigation and security services

458	Services to buildings
459	Landscape and horticultural services
460	Other support services
461	Waste management and remediation services
462	Elementary and secondary schools
463	Junior colleges, colleges, universities, and professional schools
464	Other educational services
465	Offices of physicians
466	Offices of dentists
467	Offices of other health practitioners
468	Outpatient care centers
469	Medical and diagnostic laboratories
470	Home health care services
471	Other ambulatory health care services
472	Hospitals
473	Nursing and community care facilities
474	Residential mental health, substance abuse, and other residential care facilities
475	Individual and family services
476	Child day care services
477	Community food, housing, and other relief services, including rehabilitation services
478	Performing arts companies
479	Commercial Sports Except Racing
480	Racing and Track Operation
481	Independent artists, writers, and performers
482	Promoters of performing arts and sports and agents for public figures
483	Museums, historical sites, zoos, and parks
484	Amusement parks and arcades
485	Gambling industries (except casino hotels)
486	Other amusement and recreation industries

GOVERNMENT

487	Fitness and recreational sports centers
488	Bowling centers
489	Hotels and motels, including casino hotels
490	Other accommodations
491	Full-service restaurants
492	Limited-service restaurants
493	All other food and drinking places
494	Automotive repair and maintenance, except car washes
495	Car washes
496	Electronic and precision equipment repair and maintenance
497	Commercial and industrial machinery and equipment repair and maintenance
498	Personal and household goods repair and maintenance
499	Personal care services
500	Death care services
501	Dry-cleaning and laundry services
502	Other personal services
503	Religious organizations
504	Grantmaking, giving, and social advocacy organizations
505	Business and professional associations
506	Labor and civic organizations
507	Private households
517	* Not an industry (Used and secondhand goods)
518	* Not an industry (Scrap)
519	* Not an industry (Rest of world adjustment)
520	* Not an industry (Noncomparable foreign imports)
508	Postal service
509	Federal electric utilities
510	Other federal government enterprises
512	State government electric utilities
513	Other state government enterprises
516	Other local government enterprises

521	* Employment and payroll of state govt, education
522	* Employment and payroll of state govt, hospitals and health services
523	* Employment and payroll of state govt, other services
524	* Employment and payroll of local govt, education
525	* Employment and payroll of local govt, hospitals and health services
526	* Employment and payroll of local govt, other services
527	* Employment and payroll of federal govt, military
528	* Employment and payroll of federal govt, non-military

Table S2: List of NAICS industries to estimate county-level employment for the oil and gas sector

NAICS CODE	INDUSTRY DESCRIPTION
211120	Crude Petroleum Extraction
211130	Natural Gas Extraction
213111	Drilling Oil and Gas Wells
213112	Support Activities for Oil and Gas Operations
221210	Natural Gas Distribution
221112	Fossil Fuel Electric Power Generation
486110	Pipeline Transportation of Crude Oil
486210	Pipeline Transportation of Natural Gas
486910	Pipeline Transportation of Refined Petroleum Products
486990	All Other Pipeline Transportation

Table S3: List of oil and gas occupations

O*NET-SOC 2019 CODE	O*NET-SOC 2019 TITLE
17-1022.00	Surveyors
17-2151.00	Mining and Geological Engineers, Including Mining Safety Engineers
17-2171.00	Petroleum Engineers
17-3031.00	Surveying and Mapping Technicians
47-5011.00	Derrick Operators, Oil and Gas
47-5012.00	Rotary Drill Operators, Oil and Gas
47-5013.00	Service Unit Operators, Oil and Gas
47-5071.00	Roustabouts, Oil and Gas
47-5081.00	Helpers--Extraction Workers
49-9071.00	Maintenance and Repair Workers, General
49-9096.00	Riggers
51-1011.00	First-Line Supervisors of Production and Operating Workers
51-8092.00	Gas Plant Operators
51-8093.00	Petroleum Pump System Operators, Refinery Operators, and Gaugers
51-9198.00	Helpers--Production Workers
53-7071.00	Gas Compressor and Gas Pumping Station Operators
53-7072.00	Pump Operators, Except Wellhead Pumpers
53-7073.00	Wellhead Pumpers

Table S4: List of renewable energy occupations

O*NET-SOC 2019 CODE	O*NET-SOC 2019 TITLE
11-3051.00	Industrial Production Managers
11-3071.00	Transportation, Storage, and Distribution Managers
11-9199.09	Wind Energy Operations Managers
11-9199.10	Wind Energy Development Managers
17-2051.00	Civil Engineers
17-2071.00	Electrical Engineers
17-2081.00	Environmental Engineers
17-2141.00	Mechanical Engineers
17-2199.10	Wind Energy Engineers
17-2199.11	Solar Energy Systems Engineers
17-3022.00	Civil Engineering Technologists and Technicians
17-3023.00	Electrical and Electronic Engineering Technologists and Technicians
17-3024.00	Electro-Mechanical and Mechatronics Technologists and Technicians
17-3025.00	Environmental Engineering Technologists and Technicians
17-3026.00	Industrial Engineering Technologists and Technicians
41-4011.07	Solar Sales Representatives and Assessors
47-1011.00	First-Line Supervisors of Construction Trades and Extraction Workers
47-1011.03	Solar Energy Installation Managers
47-2073.00	Operating Engineers and Other Construction Equipment Operators
47-2111.00	Electricians
47-2231.00	Solar Photovoltaic Installers
49-9041.00	Industrial Machinery Mechanics
49-9043.00	Maintenance Workers, Machinery
49-9051.00	Electrical Power-Line Installers and Repairers
49-9071.00	Maintenance and Repair Workers, General
49-9081.00	Wind Turbine Service Technicians

49-9098.00	Helpers--Installation, Maintenance, and Repair Workers
51-1011.00	First-Line Supervisors of Production and Operating Workers
51-4041.00	Machinists
51-4072.00	Molding, Coremaking, and Casting Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-4081.00	Multiple Machine Tool Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-8012.00	Power Distributors and Dispatchers
51-8013.00	Power Plant Operators
51-9012.00	Separating, Filtering, Clarifying, Precipitating, and Still Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-9023.00	Mixing and Blending Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-9032.00	Cutting and Slicing Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-9124.00	Coating, Painting, and Spraying Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders

Table S5: List of hydrogen occupations

O*NET-SOC 2019 CODE	O*NET-SOC 2019 TITLE
11-3013.00	Facilities Managers
11-3051.00	Industrial Production Managers
17-2041.00	Chemical Engineers
17-2051.00	Civil Engineers
17-2071.00	Electrical Engineers
17-2112.00	Industrial Engineers
17-2131.00	Materials Engineers
17-2141.00	Mechanical Engineers
17-2141.01	Fuel Cell Engineers
17-2199.03	Energy Engineers, Except Wind and Solar
17-3022.00	Civil Engineering Technologists and Technicians
17-3023.00	Electrical and Electronic Engineering Technologists and Technicians
17-3026.00	Industrial Engineering Technologists and Technicians
17-3027.00	Mechanical Engineering Technologists and Technicians
19-2031.00	Chemists
19-4031.00	Chemical Technicians
47-2073.00	Operating Engineers and Other Construction Equipment Operators
47-2211.00	Sheet Metal Workers
49-2094.00	Electrical and Electronics Repairers, Commercial and Industrial Equipment
49-9041.00	Industrial Machinery Mechanics
49-9043.00	Maintenance Workers, Machinery
49-9051.00	Electrical Power-Line Installers and Repairers
49-9071.00	Maintenance and Repair Workers, General
49-9098.00	Helpers--Installation, Maintenance, and Repair Workers
51-4023.00	Rolling Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic

51-4031.00	Cutting, Punching, and Press Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-4033.00	Grinding, Lapping, Polishing, and Buffing Machine Tool Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-4041.00	Machinists
51-4081.00	Multiple Machine Tool Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-4121.00	Welders, Cutters, Solderers, and Brazers
51-4122.00	Welding, Soldering, and Brazing Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-4191.00	Heat Treating Equipment Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-4193.00	Plating Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Metal and Plastic
51-6091.00	Extruding and Forming Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders, Synthetic and Glass Fibers
51-8091.00	Chemical Plant and System Operators
51-8092.00	Gas Plant Operators
51-9011.00	Chemical Equipment Operators and Tenders
51-9012.00	Separating, Filtering, Clarifying, Precipitating, and Still Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-9023.00	Mixing and Blending Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-9124.00	Coating, Painting, and Spraying Machine Setters, Operators, and Tenders
51-9198.00	Helpers--Production Workers

Table S6: List of O*NET skill requirements used in this analysis

Category	Skill
Content	Active Listening
	Mathematics
	Reading Comprehension
	Science
	Speaking
Process	Writing
	Active Learning
	Critical Thinking
	Learning Strategies
Problem Solving	Monitoring
	Complex Problem Solving
Resource Management	Management of Financial Resources
	Management of Material Resource
	Management of Personnel Resources
Social	Time Management
	Coordination
	Instructing
	Negotiation
	Persuasion
	Service Orientation
Systems	Social Perceptiveness
	Judgement and Decision Making
	Systems Analysis
Technical	Systems Evaluation
	Equipment Maintenance
	Equipment Selection
	Installation
	Operation and Control
	Operations Analysis
	Operations Monitoring
	Programming
	Repairing
	Technology Design
Troubleshooting	

Table S7: List of O*NET knowledge requirements used in this analysis

Category	Knowledge Requirement
Humanities	English Language
	Fine Arts
	Foreign Language
	History and Archeology
	Philosophy and Theology
Management	Administration and Management
	Administrative
	Customer and Personal Service
	Economics and Accounting
	Personnel and Human Resources
	Sales and Marketing
Communications	Communications and Media
	Telecommunications
Education	Educations and Training
Engineering/Tech.	Building and Construction
	Computers and Electronics
	Design
	Engineering and Technology
	Mechanical
Health	Medicine and Dentistry
	Therapy and Counseling
Law	Law and Government
	Public Safety and Security
Production	Food Production
	Production and Processing
Math & Science	Biology
	Chemistry
	Geography
	Mathematics
	Physics
	Psychology
	Sociology and Anthropology
Transportation	Transportation

Table S8: List of O*NET daily work activities used in this analysis

Category	Work Activity
Info Gathering	Estimating the Quantifiable Characteristics of Products, Events, or Information
	Identifying Objects, Actions, and Events
	Inspecting Equipment, Structures, or Materials
	Getting Information
	Monitoring Processes, Materials, or Surroundings
Administration	Monitoring and Controlling Resources
	Performing Administrative Activities
	Staffing Organizational Units
Communication	Assisting and Caring for Others
	Communicating with People Outside the Organization
	Communicating with Supervisors, Peers, or Subordinates
	Establishing and Maintaining Interpersonal Relationships
	Interpreting the Meaning of Information for Others
	Performing for or Working Directly with the Public
	Resolving Conflicts and Negotiating with Others
Coordination	Selling or Influencing Others
	Coaching and Developing Others
	Coordinating the Work and Activities of Others
	Developing and Building Teams
	Guiding, Directing, and Motivating Subordinates
Data Processing	Providing Consultation and Advice to Others
	Training and Teaching Others
	Analyzing Data or Information
	Evaluating Information to Determine Compliance with Standards
Decision Making	Judging the Qualities of Objects, Services, or People
	Processing Information
	Developing Objectives and Strategies
	Making Decisions and Solving Problems
	Organizing, Planning, and Prioritizing Work
	Scheduling Work and Activities
Technical Tasks	Thinking Creatively
	Updating and Using Relevant Knowledge
	Documenting/Recording Information
	Drafting, Laying Out, and Specifying Technical Devices, Parts, and Equipment
Manual Tasks	Repairing and Maintaining Electronic Equipment
	Repairing and Maintaining Mechanical Equipment
	Working with Computers
	Controlling Machines and Processes
	Handling and Moving Objects
	Operating Vehicles, Mechanized Devices, or Equipment
	Performing General Physical Activities

